

NOTES

TABLE 1

Dissoeiation : $\text{Al}(\text{SO}_4)_3 = \text{AlSO}_4^+ + \text{SO}_4^{2-}$

Temp. °C	K_1		ΔH cal mol ⁻¹	ΔG cal mol ⁻¹	ΔS cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	Sharma - Prasad	Our values			
5	—	0.180 82	-18 400±100	1 125.65	-52.25±0.86
15	0.816 2	0.079 48	-18 400±100	1 449.44	-51.56±0.85
25	0.158 5	0.019 06	-18 400±100	2 345.10	-52.84±0.88
35	0.089 1	0.019 18	-18 400±100	2 649.26	-52.11±0.88

Sharma and Prasad used equation (6),

instead of equation (5). Since the ionic concentration of Hg_2^{2+} ion is of the same order as that of $\text{Al}(\text{SO}_4)_3$ ion, the concentration of the former ion cannot be neglected. On adding equations (4) and (5), we get,

Similarly, multiplying equation (4) by three and adding to equation (5), we get,

On feeding the values of $[\text{H}^+]$, $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$, $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$, $[\text{Hg}_2^{2+}]$ and $[\text{Al}]_{\text{T}}$ in equation (7), we get $2[\text{Al}^{3+}] - 2[\text{Al}(\text{SO}_4)_3]$. In a very dilute solution, if a preliminary assumption is made that $\text{Al}(\text{SO}_4)_3$ ion is absent, we get the value of $[\text{Al}^{3+}]$.

In case of these solutions, the value of $[\text{AlSO}_4^+]$ is calculated from equation (8) assuming that $[\text{Al}(\text{SO}_4)_3] = 0$. We get a new value of ionic strength from equation (9),

$$\mu = \frac{1}{2}[\text{H}^+] + \frac{1}{2}[\text{HSO}_4^-] + \frac{1}{2}[\text{AlSO}_4^+] + 2[\text{SO}_4^{2-}] + 2[\text{Hg}_2^{2+}] + 4.5[\text{Al}^{3+}] \quad (9)$$

The process is repeated till μ becomes constant upto the fourth place of decimal. When we increased the concentrations beyond a certain limit, we found that $[\text{Al}^{3+}]$ was almost zero. Hence, it was decided to take concentrations slightly above this range and assume that $[\text{Al}^{3+}] = 0$.

At such high concentration, values of $[\text{H}^+]$, $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$, $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$, and $[\text{Hg}_2^{2+}]$ for an arbitrary value of μ are described as described earlier. These values of concentration for the various ionic species are put in equation (7) and it is assumed that $[\text{Al}^{3+}] = 0$. So we get a value of $[\text{Al}(\text{SO}_4)_3]$. By feeding all these values in equation (8) we get a value of $[\text{AlSO}_4^+]$. A new value of ionic strength is found from equation (10),

$$\mu = \frac{1}{2}[\text{H}^+] + \frac{1}{2}[\text{HSO}_4^-] + \frac{1}{2}[\text{AlSO}_4^+] + \frac{1}{2}[\text{Al}(\text{SO}_4)_3] + 2[\text{SO}_4^{2-}] + 2[\text{Hg}_2^{2+}] \quad (10)$$

This process is repeated till μ becomes constant up to fifth place of decimal. The concentrations of ionic species at this stage are assumed to be exact concentrations.

Now, thermodynamic dissociation constant of $\text{Al}(\text{SO}_4)_3$ is

$$K_1 = \frac{a_{\text{AlSO}_4^+} \cdot a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}}{a_{\text{Al}(\text{SO}_4)_3}} \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) can be written as

$$\log \frac{[\text{AlSO}_4^+][\text{SO}_4^{2-}]}{[\text{Al}(\text{SO}_4)_3]} - \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} = \log K_1 - b\mu \quad (12)$$

Taking a number of solutions with different ionic strengths and plotting left-hand-side of equation (12) against μ , we get linear plots at all the four temperatures. The straight lines are drawn in such a manner that equal and least number of squares lie above and below straight lines. The values of K_1 and b have been calculated from these plots at 5, 15, 25 and 35°.

A plot of $\log K_1$ against $1/T$ is linear, and the value of ΔH has been found from the slope of this plot. The values of ΔG and ΔS have been found from well-known equations. These values are presented in Table 1.

Our values of K_1 are of the same order as that of $^{\circ}\text{Cr}(\text{SO}_4)_3 = \text{CrSO}_4^+ + \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ and of $^{\circ}\text{In}(\text{SO}_4)_3 = \text{InSO}_4^+ + \text{SO}_4^{2-}$.

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